

Of Jötnar-Gygjars and Hulderfork-Huldras: Just Look through the Trolls

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They are ugly, devilish, of gigantic proportion, sometimes tiny and with unusual features, perforce live in the dark, for exposure to sunlight will turn them into stone and make them lifeless. Little wonder, some creatures in the cyber world have been given the same name. There is more in common between the two pieces of species: creatures from Norse mythology called jötnar (singular: jötunn; feminine: gygjar) and some of the real life modern day homo sapiens sapiens who hide behind their computer screens and use gutter language on the internet.

Jötnar come out of dwellings in the mountain caves only under the safety of the darkness to prey upon human beings. So do the trolls; they venture out only in the cyber world, for being active in the real world will betray their spinelessness and give away their personality: that of being severely limited in civility and chivalry. Jötnar hunt humans as they are fond of human flesh; internet trolls assassinate characters simply because they don't have one!

What do jötnar do when they are not hungry? They throw stones at

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humans and destroy settlements in the mountains. And what do the internet trolls do? When they are empty in their head and have nothing of their own to say they blurt out something to make sure people don't forget their biggest quality: command of nuisance value or being circus clowns.

Then there are the Norwegian types – Hulderfolk. The internet trolls, like hulderfolk, are smart writers, but alas like hulderfolk they are unable to hide their long tails. Why, the tails are visible simply because hulderfolk-trolls move around in their birthday suit. These trolls try to conceal their tails in their undergarment, that is, when they try to pretend to possess some civility, their tails being tails, they simply give themselves away. Of course, there are female counterparts of hulderfolk: huldras. The latter have their own charm and sometimes ensnare even the most sensible of the netizens in no time.

In the late 1980s, Internet users adopted the word “troll” to denote someone who intentionally disturbs communities online. Earlier, the term used was “flaming”. In the context of cyber world, ‘troll’ and its derivative like ‘trolling’ are recent entries to the dictionaries. Merriam-Webster defines troll as “a person who intentionally antagonizes others online by posting inflammatory, irrelevant, or offensive comments or other disruptive content.”²¹

Urban Dictionary's top rated definition for trolling (verb), as it relates to the internet, is “the deliberate act (by a troll – noun or adjective) of making random unsolicited and/or controversial comments on various internet forums with the intent to provoke an emotional knee jerk reaction from unsuspecting readers to engage in a fight or argument.”²²

According to Wikipedia, a troll is “a person who starts quarrels or upsets people on the internet to distract and sow discord by posting inflammatory and digressive, extraneous, or off-topic messages in an online community (such as a newsgroup, forum, chat room, or blog) with the intent of provoking readers into displaying emotional responses and normalizing tangential discussion, whether for the troll's amusement or a specific gain.”²³ Also, trolls often use profanities online (Moreau, 2018).

Supporters of trolling argue that it is about humour, mischief and freedom of speech. But for those at the receiving end, the ferocity and personal nature of the abuse mean plain defamation or hate speech (de Castella, and Brown, 2011). Today, the word has become a catchall for abominable online behaviour. “Trolling used be playful but annoying, a sort of virtual, comedic performance art with the end goal of getting under the skin of a selected online audience. Today the word is more often used to describe some of the most despicable

behaviors we see on the internet and social media apps, from stalking and harassment to violent threats and expressions of racism, homophobia and misogyny” (Halloway, 2016).

Happy Hunting Ground

A happy hunting ground for the trolls is the social media platforms but they go beyond these and sneak into the personal cyber domains like email and messengers of their victims. Advancement in science has given us Information Communication Technology (ICT), which, in turn, is a convergence of microelectronics, computing, telecommunications, broadcasting, and optoelectronics. The term refers to a range of internet-based and mobile services that allow users to participate in online exchanges, contribute content and join online communities.

Social media networks (SMNs) are a subset of ICT and defined as “online tools and utilities that allow communication of information online and participation and collaboration” (Newson, et al., 2008).

Often referred to as Web 2.0, the kinds of internet services which are commonly associated with social media are blogs, wikis, social bookmarking, social networking sites, status update services, virtual world content and media sharing sites (Dewing, 2012).

There is some overlap in the nature of the individual tools of social media. Blog is short form of weblog which can be hosted on websites like Wordpress, Blogspot, Weebly, Tumblr, etc; Wiki is a collective website where participants can create, edit and host content, the most prominent example being Wikipedia; bookmarking sites allow users to organize and share links to websites, examples being Reddit and Digg; social networking sites allow participants to constructed a public profile and also allow articulation of a list of participants with whom they are connected, the most popular being Facebook and LinkedIn; status update services allow users microblogging so that they can tell others about their status or an event and follow such posts by fellow users; virtual world content sites offer game-like virtual environment for users to interact in, example being Second Life in which users create an “avatar” of themselves and interact with others through those avatars (OECD, 2007); media sharing sites enable users to post audio, video, photographs, etc, popular examples being YouTube, Instagram and Pinterest.

The enormity of social media tools can be understood by taking the example of the popular site called Facebook. Launched in 2004 as a social networking website exclusively for Harvard students, Facebook as of September 2018 has

more than 2.23 billion monthly active users which is a 17 per cent increase year over year (www.statista.com, 2018).⁴ In other words, if facebookers were to be treated like a nation, then “facebook nation” will be larger than China and the US combined. Peoples of a few European countries will have to join them to outnumber the “facebookans”. Facebook users interact with other users, or Facebook friends, by updating their status, writing on the walls of other members or sending direct personal messages. Users are able to create and join interest groups, “like” pages, import and search for contacts, and upload photos and videos. Facebook, indeed, is perched right at the top of the popularity list, leaving others head and shoulder behind.

There is another significant platform: WhatsApp. Instant messaging platform WhatsApp, which has been acquired by Facebook, has grown to 1.5 billion active users worldwide. It is extremely popular in India and has more than 200 million active users (www.statista.com, 2018).⁵ The instant messaging platforms are built around the notion of private communication. Nevertheless the easy availability of WhatsApp on most phones, its easy interface, and group features that allow bulk messages to be sent, has made it one of the hottest tools of communication. WhatsApp is being used to disseminate messages, engage with fellow users, be they college group, a cultural collective, a scientific group or voters. WhatsApp allows people to send text and multimedia messages using mobile data or Wi-Fi networks free of charge, thus avoiding costly SMS messaging. A user doesn’t need to create profiles or add friends, the app links directly to his contact list so that someone can send a message to anyone in his phonebook. In the last couple of elections in India, the volunteers or social media coordinators of the political parties worked with the campaign’s main WhatsApp channel to send out image posts and messages in hope that the receivers will forward them to others and create a “human chain” of communication.

Why Do People Troll on the Internet?

Holloway (2018) cites a study to say that an estimated 5.6 per cent of people self-identify as online trolls. This translates into millions as the number of daily internet users globally is 3.58 billion (www.statista.com, 2018).⁷

These millions have their distinctive baggage and hence distinctive reasons to troll individuals or communities. The trigger could be such psycho-social issues as narcissism, catharsis, depression, anger, jealousy, loneliness, but they may not be conscious of influencing factor. There are studies to suggest why people troll and what makes trolling so easy. Among the offering *Urban*

Dictionary has is this, too “Being a prick on the internet because you can. Typically unleashing one or more cynical or sarcastic remarks on an innocent by-stander, because it’s the internet and, hey, you can.”⁷

Mark the language. So ‘trollish’, if there can be a term like this.

While the obvious reasons are the sense of safety and anonymity that computer screen provides to the trolls. They can hide behind the screen so easily and though lacking in courage to own up their statement, being able to vent out makes them feel strong.

“Strength of the weak ties” (Granovetter, 2011) explains how the internet gives its users the nerve to express themselves. While this attribute can be used by the users to bring about massive social and political mobilization and changes as it happened in Tunisia and Egypt (Stork, 2011), many use it to being a nuisance.

Chaturvedi (2016) argues says that trolling is an organized political activity in India and trolls are the Twitter equivalent of a communally charged mob out to burn down somebody’s home (or village) as part of a pogrom.

In a systematic study on trolls, Fox (2014) has listed the following eight factors why someone may post something offensive:

“Anonymity: This is one big factor that evokes that courageous instinct even in cowards to spew their infected opinions online....”

“Perceived Obscurity: Facebook users with accounts tied to their offline identities know they are not anonymous, yet they may have feelings of obscurity. The internet, they think is an unreal and virtual place. They think that they can get away with anything they post simply because people who see or read their posts are just faceless masses they will never come across in real life.”

“Perceived Majority Status: The online medium gives a false notion to people that they and their opinion enjoy majority and that is why they tend to express themselves more freely and openly. This is aptly reflected in the spiral of silence theory. Another psychology at work is that there is no fear of getting ostracised, which is usually associated with unpopular opinion that is endorsed by only a handful of people.”

“Social Identity Salience: The SIDE model, an abbreviation for social identity model of deindividuation effects says that the social identity online means more than individual identity. There is a strong sense of being a part of the society and aligning oneself with the mass rather than forming or upholding individual beliefs.”

“Surrounded by ‘Friends’: Social Media is a medium that makes everyone feel that they are with people who are their friends, although there is a sky of a gap between the virtual friendship and friendship in real world. Social media, therefore, is kind of a wishy-wishy thing with paper roses. Users feel more confident expressing themselves as they anticipate support or agreement from ‘friends’.”

“Desensitization: Over time, one of the drawbacks of being in the online environment is that we lose our sensitivity towards others. Instead of feeling bad for insulting and hurting others online, we feel okay about it. On the contrary we start finding fault with others, which is at the other end of it.”

“Personality Traits: Some people enjoy making other people uncomfortable or angry while some are by their very nature, blunt and outspoken. Personality traits such as self-righteousness and social dominance orientation (in which you think some social groups, typically yours, are inherently better than others) are related to expressing intolerance. Others are ‘hard core’ believers who will express their opinions no matter what, because they believe their opinion is infallible.”

“Perceived Lack of Consequences: The theory of social exchange suggests that we analyze the costs and benefits in our communication and relationships. The false sense of anonymity and obscurity makes individuals believe that they will not be personally responsible for their conduct or misconduct.”

Pasricha (2016), in her study “Cyber Violence Against Women In India”, reports, “India, as elsewhere in the world, online harassment of women and marginalized genders and sexualities is rampant, in contrast to Internet’s initial premise of equal opportunity and neutrality. What we have today is a flawed internet that reflects the offline world we live in, where women and marginalized communities are abused, harassed, threatened, stalked and violated on a daily basis.”

Trolling as a phenomenon has swept across websites in recent years, yet the technology it uses is innovating every day. Hence not all societies have been able to have a comprehensive legal framework to stop or regulate it. Punishments have ranged from gentle rap on the knuckles to being put behind bars (de Castell and Brown, 2011).

What the Law Says

In the UK, the Communications Act, 2003, governs the internet, email, mobile phone calls and text messaging. Under section 127 of the act it is an

offence to send messages that are “grossly offensive or of an indecent, obscene or menacing character.” The offence occurs whether those targeted actually receive the message or not.

In India, the Information Technology Act, 2000, governs much of the internet play and the players. Based on the UN Model Law on Electronic Commerce 1996 (UNCITRAL Model) recommended by the General Assembly of the UN by a resolution dated January 30, 1997, the Indian act is the primary law in dealing with cybercrime and electronic commerce. The original Act contained 94 sections, divided in 13 chapters and four schedules. The law applies to the whole of India and people of nationalities can also be indicted if the crime involves a computer or network located in India.

A major amendment in 2008 introduced the Section 66A which penalized sending of “offensive messages.” It had provisions of imprisonment up to three years, with fine.

The amendment also introduced the Section 69, which gave authorities the power of “interception or monitoring or decryption of any information through any computer resource.” child porn, cyber terrorism, and voyeurism. It was passed on 22 December 2008 without any debate in Lok Sabha. The next day it was passed by Rajya Sabha. The then President Pratibha Patil gave it her assent on February 5, 2009. The punishment prescribed is imprisonment up to seven years and fine up to Rs 1,000,000.

On March 24, 2015, the Supreme Court of India, gave the verdict that Section 66A is unconstitutional in entirety. Section 66A of IT Act 2000 is “arbitrarily, excessively and disproportionately invades the right of free speech” provided under Article 19(1) of the Constitution of India. However, the court turned down a plea to strike down sections 69A and 79 of the Act, which deal with the procedure and safeguards for blocking certain websites.

Some High Profile Cases

One of the first high-profile cases emerged in the US state of Missouri in 2006, when 13-year-old Megan Meier killed herself after being bullied online. The bully, Lori Drew, was a middle-aged neighbour who had set up a MySpace account to win – and later betray – her trust. Drew was acquitted of unauthorised computer use in 2009 due to concerns that a conviction would criminalise false online identities (de Castella and Brown, 2011).

In a first, Colm Coss was imprisoned in 2010 for posting obscene messages on Facebook tribute sites, including that of reality show participant Jade Goody

who later died. The following year, Sean Duffy was jailed for 18 weeks after posting offensive messages and videos on tribute pages about young people who had died. One of those he targeted was 15-year-old Natasha MacBryde, who had been killed by a train. “I fell asleep on the track lolz” was one of the messages he left on a Facebook page set up by her family (de Castella and Brown, 2011).

In India, the targets have ranged from commoners like college students to celebrities like film actors and sportspersons. India’s first conviction for cyber-stalking since cyber-laws came into existence in 2000 was by a Mumbai court which sent Yogesh Prabhu, 36, an executive in a private company, to jail for three months. In March 2009, Prabhu had sent a series of emails from an anonymous address to a colleague who had earlier rejected his proposal.

This was not the first cyber-stalking case in India. Documents show it was in 2001, when Manish Kathuria was arrested by Delhi Police for impersonating a woman in an internet chatroom. Kathuria was charged under Indian Penal Code (IPC) for “outraging the modesty” of his victim Ritu Kohli. Kathuria would pretend to be her, use obscene language, give out her home phone number and invite callers. That IPC section, however, did not cover internet crimes, and Pavan Duggal, Delhi-based cyber-law expert who worked on the case, explains that it finally fizzled out when a frustrated Kohli moved out of India (Roy, 2015).

Journalist Barkha Dutt has faced vitriol on the internet for her views. She has chronicled it in graphic language in a series “Let’s talk about trolls” in the daily *The Hindustan Times* (Dutt, 2017). Gurmehar Kaur, the daughter of a martyred Indian soldier, was trolled viciously when she advocated peace between India and Pakistan. She wrote about it in the same series run by *The Hindustan Times* (Kaur, 2017).

In 2012, 21-year-old girl Shaheen Dhada from Palghar in Mumbai was severely abused and threatened when she posted a message on Facebook criticising the shutdown in Mumbai for the funeral of Bal Thackeray. Another 20-year-old girl and Rinu Srinivasan got the same treatment for “liking” the post (BBC, 2012).

Earlier this year, a Kerala college student was abused for selling fish in her college uniform. She said she was raising money to pay for her education. The troll was later arrested. Incidentally, the girl Hanan Hamid (Chitra, 2018).

Actor Shruti Seth saw the hate flood unleash on her when she questioned Prime Minister Narendra Modi who had asked Indians to tweet pictures with their daughters. Thousands responded with the #SelfieWithDaughter hashtag,

but she was one of the critics of the “tokenism”. As Seth puts it, the “floodgates of hell opened, I was subjected to a tsunami of hate. Men spewed sexual abuse shortly after posting selfies with their daughters.” It was worse for activist Kavita Krishnan, who tweeted: “Careful before sharing #SelfieWithDaughter with #LameDuckPM. He has a record of stalking daughters.” She was referring to an allegation that police in the western state of Gujarat had spied on a young woman in 2009, at the behest of Mr Modi, who was then the state’s chief minister. She was attacked online, with some men posting graphic threats on her Facebook page. “Modi supporters threatened me with rape,” she said (Roy, 2015).

Popular daily The Telegraph once compiled celebrities who had got trolled for one reason or the other. These celebrities included actors Alia Bhatt, AlokNath, Neil Nitin Mukesh, Dany Danzongpa, Tiger Shroff, and Prime Minister Narendra Modi. The venom varied from attack on perceived lack of intelligence (Bhatt), to name (Modi, Shroff and Mukesh), onscreen identity of villain (Danzongpa). Enough to show that the attack can come on some flimsy ground. Do one need to recall the *Urban Dictionary* explanation cited above as to why people troll? (*The Hindustan Times*, 2017).

How to Deal with Trolls

That trolling is rampant and it can happen to anybody is obvious. So, what does one do to deal with the trolls? Suggestions are many: give them a befitting retort, take to the police, track and publicly shame them, simply ignore them.... Giving examples, de Castella and Brown (2011) write, “Twitter has given the public direct access to celebrities. And stars, including Stephen Fry and Miranda Hart, have temporarily left the website after coming under fire. Internet experts say the key is not to ‘feed the troll’ by offering them a response. Comedian Dom Joly takes a different approach.”

Moreau (2018) suggests, “If a troll tries to provoke you, just ignore them. They’re not worth your time or emotional distress. Try not to take anything personally and remind yourself that their bad behavior does not change who you are.”

According to Moreau, a person who seems like a troll is actually the one suffering in some way and is trying to distract themselves and make themselves feel better by taking it out on you. “If you’re feeling strong enough, you might even consider responding to them with kindness by complimenting something about them (such as their profile picture, their username, etc). This is the last thing they’ll expect from you, and while you’ll have to risk being trolled again, there’s always a chance that your unexpected kindness could move them in a way that changes their behavior for the better.”

Each type of response has its merit, and of course, limitation. For example, Pasricha (2016) found only a third of respondents in her study had reported harassment to law enforcement; among them, 38 per cent characterized the response as “not at all helpful.” In the same study, Pasricha found that mechanisms to report abuse on social media platforms fall short. Victims are more likely to block abuse than to report it, yet blocking is ineffective against organized, sustained campaigns using multiple accounts.

What are Social Media Platforms Doing

Thanks to the frequent outrage against the vitriol on social media, especially in plying of fake news and rumours that lead to violence and loss of lives and wealth, platforms promoters have been making efforts to control the trolls. Sometimes they do so on their own and sometimes they are mandated by the governments concerned. For example, the Government of India has recently mandated that social media promoters will be held accountable for the content on them (Pahwa, 2018).⁹

Almost all the popular social media platforms have their origins in the developed western world which places a premium on free speech and other higher human values like right to life and liberty. For example, while Facebook generally promotes free speech, it employs some exceptions on hateful or harassing posts. Facebook also has profanity filters. Similarly, YouTube allows contributors to regulate the traffic but enabling them to limit access to the stuff they upload on the platform.

Article 19 of the UNDHR protects free speech but concern about the misuse of this right on the platforms is growing. Facebook’s former marketing director Randi Zuckerberg and Google head Eric Schmidt have both suggested anonymous posting should be phased out (de Castella and Brown, 2011).

While many think that regulation is needed, it must be kept in mind that the internet does not create special threats. It is the people in the public sphere who blurt things offensive. The approach should be to not throw the baby with bathwater. Social media fora and newspaper websites could well employ moderators to prevent the comments descending into hate mongering. Banning online anonymity could be considered, but that would also amount to exposing or even dissuading the whistleblowers to do the yeoman job that they do. Jöttnar, gygjars, huderfolk and huldras may be mythical creatures in folklore, but their counterparts exist for the real in the cyberworld. They will be there. Curtailing free speech and trampling upon civil liberties to stop the aberrant few is not a price worth paying.

Notes

1. Merriam-Webster, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/troll>
2. Urban Dictionary, <https://www.urbandictionary.com/define.php?term=Trolling>
3. “Internet troll”, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Internet_troll
4. This statistic shows a timeline with the worldwide number of monthly active Facebook users from 2008 to 2018. As of the second quarter of 2018, Facebook had 2.23 billion monthly active users. In the third quarter of 2012, the number of active Facebook users had surpassed one billion, making it the first social network ever to do so. Active users are those which have logged in to Facebook during the last 30 days. Furthermore, as of the previous quarter the social network had 1.74 billion mobile MAU. The platform is also the most popular social network worldwide.
5. This statistic shows a timeline with the amount of monthly active WhatsApp users worldwide as of December 2017. As of that month, the mobile messaging app announced more than 1.5 billion monthly active users, up from over 1 billion MAU in February 2016. The service is one of the most popular mobile apps worldwide.
6. This statistic gives information on the total number of worldwide internet users from 2005 to 2017. As of the most recent reported period, the number of internet users worldwide was 3.58 billion, up from 3.39 billion in the previous year. Easier access to computers, the modernization of countries around the world and an increased utilization of smartphones has given people the opportunity to use the internet more frequently and with more convenience. However, internet penetration often pertains to the current state of development regarding communications networks. As of March 2017, there were approximately 731 million total internet users in China and 287 million total internet users in the United States. However, broadband internet usage is not equally present in many countries and due to infrastructure reasons, developing online markets rely strongly on mobile connections. Subsequently, global mobile data traffic is set to surpass 49 exabytes per month in 2021, up from 7 exabytes per month as of 2016. Social networking is one of the most popular online activities and Facebook is the most popular online network based on active usage. As of the fourth quarter of 2016, there were a total of roughly 1.86 billion monthly active Facebook users, accounting for almost half of internet users worldwide. Connecting with family and friends, expressing opinions, entertainment and online shopping are amongst the most popular reasons for internet usage.
7. Urban Dictionary, <https://www.urbandictionary.com/define.php?term=Trolling>; Indian Information Technology Minister Ravi Shankar Prasad in said in the Rajya Sabha (the upper house of Parliament) on the July 26, 2018 that a social media platform cannot evade their “responsibility, accountability and larger commitment to ensure that its platform is not misused on a large scale to spread incorrect facts projected as news and designed to instigate people to commit crime.” He also said that “if they do not take adequate and prompt action, then the law of abetment also applies to them.”

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